

Extended Data

Extended Figure S1

A. Amino acid sequence alignment of the homologs of Hse1

H. sapiens1	: MPLFAT--NPFDDVEKATISMTAEDWGLILDICDRVGGSRGTG--PDCLESLIMRRVNHKDPHVAQALITLDCACVSNCGKIFHLEVSQSRDFASVSNVLI--NCGH--KVCCEKLA : 110
H. sapiens2	: MPLFTA--NPFDDVEKATINPYNTTEDVSLIMDIDCRVGGSTPNG--AKDCLRAIMKRVNHKVPHVVALQALITLDCACVSNCGKIFHLEVSQSRDFATVYRAVKNIAH--KVCCEKLA : 111
A. gambiae	: NSLFGTSS--PFDADVEKATISMTAEDWGLILDICDRVNGSAT--PDCLEKCIKRLNSPDPHVMKAITLDCACVSNCGKIFHLEVSQSRDFATVYRAVKNIAH--KVCCEKLA : 111
A. mellifera	: NSLFGTSS--PFDADVEKATISMTAEDWGLILDICDRVGGSTQ--AKDCLRSIKRYSPPHVMKAITLDCACVSNCGKIFHLEVSQSRDFATVYRAVKNIAH--KVCCEKLA : 111
A. pisum	: MGSLLSS--SFDADVEKATISMTAEDWGLILDICDRVAGSSVN--AKDCLRSIKRYSPPHVMKAITLDCACVSNCGKIFHLEVSQSRDFATVYRAVKNIAH--KVCCEKLA : 112
B. mori	: MGFGTSS--PFDADVEKATISMTAEDWGLILDICDRVAGSST--AKELRAVMRRLAHPDPHVMKAITLDCACVSNCGKIFHLEVSQSRDFATVYRAVKNIAH--KVCCEKLA : 111
D. melanogaster	: MGFGTSS--PFDADVEKATISMTAEDWGLILDICDRVAGSST--AKELRAVMRRLAHPDPHVMKAITLDCACVSNCGKIFHLEVSQSRDFATVYRAVKNIAH--KVCCEKLA : 111
D. plexippus	: MGFGTSS--PFDADVEKATISMTAEDWGLILDICDRVAGSST--AKELRAVMRRLAHPDPHVMKAITLDCACVSNCGKIFHLEVSQSRDFATVYRAVKNIAH--KVCCEKLA : 111
P. corporis	: MGFGTSS--PFDADVEKATISMTAEDWGLILDICDRVAGSST--AKELRAVMRRLAHPDPHVMKAITLDCACVSNCGKIFHLEVSQSRDFATVYRAVKNIAH--KVCCEKLA : 111
S. frugiperda	: MGFGTSS--PFDADVEKATISMTAEDWGLILDICDRVAGSST--AKELRAVMRRLAHPDPHVMKAITLDCACVSNCGKIFHLEVSQSRDFATVYRAVKNIAH--KVCCEKLA : 111
T. castaneum	: MGFGTSS--PFDADVEKATISMTAEDWGLILDICDRVAGSST--AKELRAVMRRLAHPDPHVMKAITLDCACVSNCGKIFHLEVSQSRDFATVYRAVKNIAH--KVCCEKLA : 111
S. cerevisiae	: ---MSSAIKIRNALAKADPKLRSDNQYLLVCDLVKEDPEDNGQEVLSLLEKRLLEQQANVITRTSLTVSLAENCGSRLRQLISKNNTSLYALLESHSVHTLTKKAVTD : 112
H. sapiens1	: LMVEITD--BFNDPQLSLSATIKNLKQEGVTPPAIGSQA--EQAASPALVAKDPTGTVANKKDEEDLAKAELSLKKEQKQST-----TLSTLPTSTSSL----- : 204
H. sapiens2	: LMVEISL--BFKQKQPSLSATIKSMVEEGITPPAGSQTV--SAAA--KNGTSSNKNKDEEDLAKAELSLKKEQKQST-----ETKSLYPSSEIQ----- : 198
A. gambiae	: TKRRIADVDFISDPQLDTPSYRKLDEGHDFNDPSAT--P-----KRETTLSKDPNVSSQKDEEDLAKAELSLKKEVNTQSPKM--MS--SSGTSASSLYPSA----- : 207
A. mellifera	: LTKRIADVDFISDPQLDTPSYRKLDEGHDFNDPSAT--P-----KRTTFLSKDPNVNSQKDEEDLAKAELSLKKEKKAHNGASSHN--SPSTKYTSLYPNVSS----- : 210
A. pisum	: LTKRIADVDFISDPQLDTPSYRKLDEGHDFNDPSAT--P-----KSAKSDLVSLQKQVDDLAKAELSLKKEKKAHNGASSHN--SPSTKYTSLYPNVSS----- : 193
B. mori	: LTKRIADVDFISDPQLDTPSYRKLDEGHDFNDPSAT--P-----APSPAPAAQRQDEELAKAELSLKKEKKAHNGASSHN--SPSTKYTSLYPNVSS----- : 192
D. melanogaster	: VLKRIADVDFISDPQLDTPSYRKLDEGHDFNDPSAT--P-----AEKAAALPKDPNVSSQKDEEDLAKAELSLKKEKKAHNGASSHN--SPSTKYTSLYPNVSS----- : 222
D. plexippus	: VLKRIADVDFISDPQLDTPSYRKLDEGHDFNDPSAT--P-----AEKAAALPKDPNVSSQKDEEDLAKAELSLKKEKKAHNGASSHN--SPSTKYTSLYPNVSS----- : 212
P. corporis	: VLKRIADVDFISDPQLDTPSYRKLDEGHDFNDPSAT--P-----AEKAAALPKDPNVSSQKDEEDLAKAELSLKKEKKAHNGASSHN--SPSTKYTSLYPNVSS----- : 204
S. frugiperda	: VLKRIADVDFISDPQLDTPSYRKLDEGHDFNDPSAT--P-----AEKAAALPKDPNVSSQKDEEDLAKAELSLKKEKKAHNGASSHN--SPSTKYTSLYPNVSS----- : 190
T. castaneum	: ALKRIADVDFISDPQLDTPSYRKLDEGHDFNDPSAT--P-----KKSAPVSKDPNVSSQKDEEDLAKAELSLKKEKKAHNGASSHN--SPSTKYTSLYPNVSS----- : 207
S. cerevisiae	: ---VKQLSDSFDDESIRAMGDLYDKIRKAPYLQPNVPEK-----HNMSTQADNSDDEELAKAELSLKKEKKAHNGASSHN--SPSTKYTSLYPNVSS----- : 207
H. sapiens1	: ---LTHNHGHEGRVRAIYDFAAEDNDELTKFAGHITVLDSDSDNWWKGNETH--QGITLFPNSFVTAALIAEPEMIKT--EKKTQVFSDDVQV-----ETIEPEPEPA : 300
H. sapiens2	: ---LNN--KVARKVRAIYDFAAEDNDELTKFAGHITVLDSDSDNWWKGNETH--RGLTLPNSFVTAALIAEPEMIKT--EKKTQVFSDDVQV-----ETIEPEPEPA : 290
A. gambiae	: ---LLSTAPAEPRVRAIYDFAAEDNDELTKFAGHITVLDSDSDNWWKGNETH--RGLTLPNSFVTAALIAEPEMIKT--EKKTQVFSDDVQV-----ETIEPEPEPA : 316
A. mellifera	: ---ALGTSNAEGRVRAIYDFAAEDNDELTKFAGHITVLDSDSDNWWKGNETH--RGLTLPNSFVTAALIAEPEMIKT--EKKTQVFSDDVQV-----ETIEPEPEPA : 314
A. pisum	: ---TDRAVLYKVKVRAIYDFAAEDNDELTKFAGHITVLDSDSDNWWKGNETH--RGLTLPNSFVTAALIAEPEMIKT--EKKTQVFSDDVQV-----ETIEPEPEPA : 284
B. mori	: RVET--AP--APVRAIYDFAAEDNDELTKFAGHITVLDSDSDNWWKGNETH--RGLTLPNSFVTAALIAEPEMIKT--EKKTQVFSDDVQV-----ETIEPEPEPA : 280
D. melanogaster	: SAEASSAPAEPRVRAIYDFAAEDNDELTKFAGHITVLDSDSDNWWKGNETH--RGLTLPNSFVTAALIAEPEMIKT--EKKTQVFSDDVQV-----ETIEPEPEPA : 336
D. plexippus	: RVEAVTPTVYVRAIYDFAAEDNDELTKFAGHITVLDSDSDNWWKGNETH--RGLTLPNSFVTAALIAEPEMIKT--EKKTQVFSDDVQV-----ETIEPEPEPA : 310
P. corporis	: ---AINTPSEGRVRAIYDFAAEDNDELTKFAGHITVLDSDSDNWWKGNETH--RGLTLPNSFVTAALIAEPEMIKT--EKKTQVFSDDVQV-----ETIEPEPEPA : 300
S. frugiperda	: RVDADPAA--PRVRAIYDFAAEDNDELTKFAGHITVLDSDSDNWWKGNETH--RGLTLPNSFVTAALIAEPEMIKT--EKKTQVFSDDVQV-----ETIEPEPEPA : 287
T. castaneum	: NSSTNSIPVKEPRVRAIYDFAAEDNDELTKFAGHITVLDSDSDNWWKGNETH--RGLTLPNSFVTAALIAEPEMIKT--EKKTQVFSDDVQV-----ETIEPEPEPA : 311
S. cerevisiae	: APAHKIAPQIVVRAIYDFAAEDNDELTKFAGHITVLDSDSDNWWKGNETH--RGLTLPNSFVTAALIAEPEMIKT--EKKTQVFSDDVQV-----ETIEPEPEPA : 294
H. sapiens1	: FIDEDKIDRLHLLHEADPQCDTS--DTQEM--DLEPEL--HLEAMCHMGPLIDEKLEDEDRKHSLESELNWKVLEALSLYTKLNNEDPMYSYAKLV-----NQPYMYSQSG : 398
H. sapiens2	: YIDEDKIDRLHLLHEADPQCDTS--DTQEM--DLEPEL--DLEIDCQMGMLIDEKLEDEDRKHSLESELNWKVLEALSLYTKLNNEDPMYSYAKLV-----PPAHYPASS : 388
A. gambiae	: EINEKIDRLHLLHEADPQCDTS--DTQEM--DLEPEL--QLDQLVQMGMLIDAEELERVDRKHAQLTQSSDLDALNLYHTIMREPRDSAMMSGGVPPAGGAYTGGYGGSSM : 423
A. mellifera	: EIDEDKIDRLHLLHEADPQCDTS--DTQEM--DLEPEL--DLEBQVTAAGMLIDAEELERVDRKHAQLTQSSDLDALNLYHTIMREPRDSAMMSGGVPPAGGAYTGGYGGSSM : 404
A. pisum	: EIDEDKIDRLHLLHEADPQCDTS--DTQEM--DLEPEL--DLEBAQANMGMLIDAEELERVDRKHAQLTQSSDLDALNLYHTIMREPRDSAMMSGGVPPAGGAYTGGYGGSSM : 382
B. mori	: GIDEDKIDRLHLLHEADPQCDTS--DTQEM--DLEPEL--RDEARAAATCALVDAAERARHARLQLSADLDALNLYHTIMREPRDSAMMSGGVPPAGGAYTGGYGGSSM : 375
D. melanogaster	: RIDEDKIDRLHLLHEADPQCDTS--DTQEM--DLEPEL--RDEARAAATCALVDAAERARHARLQLSADLDALNLYHTIMREPRDSAMMSGGVPPAGGAYTGGYGGSSM : 437
D. plexippus	: RIDEDKIDRLHLLHEADPQCDTS--DTQEM--DLEPEL--RDEARAAATCALVDAAERARHARLQLSADLDALNLYHTIMREPRDSAMMSGGVPPAGGAYTGGYGGSSM : 406
P. corporis	: VIDEDKIDRLHLLHEADPQCDTS--DTQEM--DLEPEL--EIAEEVYAMGMLIDAEELERVDRKHAQLTQSSDLDALNLYHTIMREPRDSAMMSGGVPPAGGAYTGGYGGSSM : 390
S. frugiperda	: CIDEDKIDRLHLLHEADPQCDTS--DTQEM--DLEPEL--RDEARAAATCALVDAAERARHARLQLSADLDALNLYHTIMREPRDSAMMSGGVPPAGGAYTGGYGGSSM : 384
T. castaneum	: EINEKIDRLHLLHEADPQCDTS--DTQEM--DLEPEL--KIDREVNLMGMLIDAEELERVDRKHAQLTQSSDLDALNLYHTIMREPRDSAMMSGGVPPAGGAYTGGYGGSSM : 416
S. cerevisiae	: ---KTTIDQLHNSLNAISKT-----GNSNEVLDQPHIGDLYGVSVTPLRQVTRMLGKYAKKEDMLSRQVLANAERSNQLMDRAANAHSPP-----VPGALYAGMTH : 393
H. sapiens1	: V-----SGSQVYAGPPPSGAYLVAG--NAQMS-----HLQSYSLPEQLSSLSQ-----AV-----VPPSANPALPSQQTQAAYPNT : 463
H. sapiens2	: G-----VPMQTYPVQSHGGNMGQS--IHQVT-----VAQSYSLGPDQIGLRS-----LPPNVNSVTAQAQATSYLST : 451
A. gambiae	: NPMYGMFAMYSQLPGVGMYPGSPQPPSPMGYGMTHLRHDMTQMNVGTMPPQFPTPA--QQPPQQAGMHHLSHQHQ--HSMQTYA--QNGPT--TNG : 513
A. mellifera	: ---MPPHINPYQFNQGGPPPHIFNG-----VPP-----AHQT-----SFPVGGG-----PSGPY--NAT : 449
A. pisum	: QHMI--HPQHMVYNGMA-----NYAPLVEHYMPSGQVPPVTHMMP--RPNIGQMHEQPSYQMPNMQNIPNYYQVYGGHVSFESLPLQV : 467
B. mori	: P-----AHPRC----- : 381
D. melanogaster	: AALYGA-----PGYPAAGGFPFPAQNYPGM-----HSMYGPVNPPTSAPSQAPGPGYLGQP--QGQVP-----LPYQNGHAAQMNSLPAHLTOPTGTAPM : 523
D. plexippus	: PPPP-----PGALLPGPL-----SLAHPHP-----QPPRC----- : 432
P. corporis	: ---N-----YGYMIP-----N-----PPP-----VHQV-----QFNGAA-----SNQPY--VPA : 421
S. frugiperda	: PHGPHG-----PGLPPPYPYPPA-----FGPPPLHP-----PPPRC----- : 416
T. castaneum	: QT-----YNGLPPPPQPTSMPLPPGMAP-----PPGMHYATPMSTAG--MPPPPPQLMHQMPDDRRT-----QSYGSMV-----LPNPPSGVAGSQT : 494
S. cerevisiae	: A--NNTPVMPQRQSYQSNY--SPYENSLPIQHPTSANNTPYQYDLYGSV--VSQPPGYEQ : 452
H. sapiens1	: MVSSVQNGTYPSPQAPVYPPPA--ATAA-----AATADVLYQ-----NAGNMPQVNPYNLTSSTLPQPGGSSQPPQPPQYPSQKALL----- : 540
H. sapiens2	: GQDYSNPTYMNGNSNLQSATGTTAYTQM--GMSVDMSSYQ-----NTSNLPLQAGFPVTPAHPVA-----QHTNYHQPLL----- : 525
A. gambiae	: MLS-----QGAPPTTSLAGVNGQQQQQSTTSVAPQTPMMPMPQQQLGGMPQGFANP--TSPPVGMGSGPPSHQM--QP--APPNQQTLPLQMPR : 602
A. mellifera	: ---I--PTS DY-----MGSASMPNIT-----LPQHFHMQ--PPGPHQ--PPGPHQ--VP--EQSNLYP : 498
A. pisum	: ---MNYVPPQ--QPPSQ : 480
B. mori	: --- : -
D. melanogaster	: ---PQPIY-----TQPTVYTTQQQQPLPQHPQQ--PPQQGQQPPQHPNSYHIDPQSYAQVPPAVTIQQPQ : 588
D. plexippus	: --- : -
P. corporis	: ---NY-----SVVPGN-----IPQPPFNG--PPPPP--PQVGHYIA--DP--S : 454
S. frugiperda	: --- : -
T. castaneum	: LIH-----NGPPPQ-----SQSQHYMPASSANP--K : 518
S. cerevisiae	: --- : -

H. sapiens1	:	-----	:	-
H. sapiens2	:	-----	:	-
A. gambiae	:	GGGQPPVSYSPYVPPQQQQQPPVYQQMPQTAIPQGMGAGGPPPPSAQPNANHHNQQQMSMPAHYPPPTSGAPTHHHPPQQQQQPPQQQQFMPQMGPPQMTNPPMGPAMNMF	:	717
A. mellifera	:	SHQGY-----PPQTGMPMG-----PYGPPGTPPPVY-QQPQ-YAPPNGQHMM-----	:	539
A. pisum	:	-----	:	-
B. mori	:	-----	:	-
D. melanogaster	:	QPPAP-HAYMSPQHQA-PPPQYQPGPN-----LYPGNGSPA-VVNPQSYMSPQQQQQHP-----PPHQFSQLHQQAAMS	:	659
D. plexippus	:	-----	:	-
P. corporis	:	-----RSY-----PVVK-----	:	461
S. frugiperda	:	-----	:	-
T. castaneum	:	-----	:	-
S. cerevisiae	:	-----	:	-
H. sapiens1	:	-----	:	-
H. sapiens2	:	-----	:	-
A. gambiae	:	PGGPGGIGGPLSINTNHQGPQNIPIYQQR	:	747
A. mellifera	:	-----	:	-
A. pisum	:	-----	:	-
B. mori	:	-----	:	-
D. melanogaster	:	MAGGPPVGPAGYHMQNDAYKNNIPIYQQR	:	689
D. plexippus	:	-----	:	-
P. corporis	:	-----	:	-
S. frugiperda	:	-----	:	-
T. castaneum	:	-----	:	-
S. cerevisiae	:	-----	:	-

B. Amino acid sequence alignment of the homologs of Vps27

H. sapiens	:	-----MCGSGTGERLDRKTSQIL-----DETWESTLQCDLIRGQIQARYVNSIKKKVND-----KHFVALYALEVMESVKNQGT-----HDEVANKQTMDEKDLARQV-EVNV	:	105
A. gambiae	:	MEREVCFD-VIIRPNLENLTSNIN-----LEPDWQALLVQCDLIRGQVGNARYVGLAKKKMQS-----PNTITAMYALLTLESIVKNQGT-----HDEANKANGDLFQNLNTIK-HDEV	:	108
A. mellifera	:	MPSSSLTDFKLDKLTSHH-----LEPDWAILQCDLIRGQVQPKAAIAIKKMTN-----ANFVALPALVLESQVKNQGLHDEITGKQYMQKELYKTT-HENVK	:	105
A. pisum	:	MFR-SNPEKLDKVTSNL-----LEADWPTLQCDLIRGQVQPKALNAIKKKLIS-----PNTITAMYSLLVLECOVKNQGLHDEVGKRPFMQRETIKTP-HENVK	:	103
B. mori	:	MFR-ANNDFKLDKVTSNR-----LDPDWPTLQCDLIRGNDCTPKYAAVAVKKKLYS-----QNFHQAAMPALLTLESIVKNQGSGLHDEVTSKAFQCMRDLYKTTQ-HENLR	:	104
D. melanogaster	:	MFR-SSDKNLENVTSNR-----LEPDWPSILQCDLIRGNDKVTPKYFAAIKKKMS-----PNTHSSCSLLVLESIVKNQGAPTHDEVFTKENCDFMSSSELESTP-HENVR	:	103
D. plexippus	:	MFR-ANNDFKLDKVTSNR-----LDPDWPSILQCDLIRGNDVSPKYYAAVAVKKKLYS-----QNFYQAMPALLTLESIVKNQGSGLHDEVASKAFQCMRDLYKTTQ-HENLR	:	104
P. corporis	:	MRS-----CIRGCT-VSFYSSR-----YNYLSNLSLMLVANNIKKKIVN-----HNFHVAITPALVLESVKNQGHVHDEITAFRAFMEQLQELKTT-HQVVK	:	92
S. frugiperda	:	MFR-ANNDFKLDKVTSNR-----LDPDWPTLQCDLIRGNDVSPKYYAAVAVKKKLYS-----QNFHQAAMPALLVLESIVKNQGSGLHDEVTSKAFQCMRDLYKTTQ-HENLR	:	104
T. castaneum	:	MFRITGNDKLDKVTSNL-----LEPDWPSILQCDLIRGNDVQPKHAAVAVKKKLPF-----PNTITAMYALLVLESVKNQGYPLHDEITIRPFCDTLYDAKTP-HIVYR	:	105
S. cerevisiae	:	MSVSTPSELDALEQTSESIPNGDLLEIADLESDVLSRRRVKDSIRGKRRKLNADNTQSSWKLTVIKVKNQPTPIKESQREMDTLEHLIREDNSDELS	:	111

H. sapiens	:	NKLLYLQAWAFARNPKYKAVQDTNYLRAEYKFPFLK-----ESDAMFAERLEPWDAECHRRCVQFGWLRKHHCRACGIFCGKSSYSYIPKGLKERVVCGEY	:	216
A. gambiae	:	AKLLELQAWAFARNPKYKAVQDTNYLRAEYKFPFLK-----EADAMFSSDIADPWGDVCHRRCVQFGWLRKHHCRACGIVFCQSSANSILPKGLKERVVCGEY	:	219
A. mellifera	:	NKLLLELQAWAFARNPKYKAVQDTNYLRAEYKFPFLK-----ESDAMFIADTAPADGDVCHRRCVQFGWLRKHHCRACGIVFCQSSANSILPKGLKERVVCGEY	:	216
A. pisum	:	NKLLLELQAWAFARNPKYKAVQDTNYLRAEYKFPFLK-----ESDAMFSSDAPGWEDVCHRRCVQFGWLRKHHCRACGIVFCQSSANSILPKGLKERVVCGEY	:	214
B. mori	:	SKLLELQAWAFARNPKYKAVQDTNYLRAEYKFPFLK-----ESDAMFSADTAPADGDVCHRRCVQFGWLRKHHCRACGIVFCQSSANSILPKGLKERVVCGEY	:	215
D. melanogaster	:	QKMLELQAWAFARNPKYKAVQDTNYLRAEYKFPFLK-----EADAMFIADTAPADGDVCHRRCVQFGWLRKHHCRACGIVFCQSSANSILPKGLKERVVCGEY	:	214
D. plexippus	:	TKLLELQAWAFARNPKYKAVQDTNYLRAEYKFPFLK-----ESDAMFSADTAPADGDVCHRRCVQFGWLRKHHCRACGIVFCQSSANSILPKGLKERVVCGEY	:	215
P. corporis	:	AKYVELQAWAFARNPKYKAVQDTNYLRAEYKFPFLK-----ESDAMFYAHTAPADGDVCHRRCVQFGWLRKHHCRACGIVFCQSSANSILPKGLKERVVCGEY	:	203
S. frugiperda	:	NKLLLELQAWAFARNPKYKAVQDTNYLRAEYKFPFLK-----ESDAMFSADTAPADGDVCHRRCVQFGWLRKHHCRACGIVFCQSSANSILPKGLKERVVCGEY	:	215
T. castaneum	:	QKLELQAWAFARNPKYKAVQDTNYLRAEYKFPFLK-----ESDAMFSDSADTAPADGDVCHRRCVQFGWLRKHHCRACGIVFCQSSANSILPKGLKERVVCGEY	:	216
S. cerevisiae	:	ELKLLIYELVAFNDSQNLAKVYDLISRIKFPFLK-----STPEDELELRKALSLRERNSA-----SPEIPVVSVEKNEVKKQIEEIEE	:	302

H. sapiens	:	EQLNKAEGK-----ATSTTELPPEVLTSPSSQS-----QLPPKIDETALQEEELQALALSQSEABEKERLRKQKSTYTSYKAEPMPSASSAPASSLYSSPVNSAPLAEDI	:	322
A. gambiae	:	AQLQRFAGTL-----VYKPTDEEDLPABYLSSSL-AQQA-QGPARKTDEELREBEELQALALSQSEABTKQQAARRSATFHSKAPESPEPQTPQ-----AQVKRSPSPAEEPPA	:	323
A. mellifera	:	EQLNKTSTAQ-----IKAEDLPABYLSSSL-AQQQ-QVPPRKTAEELQEEELQALALSQSEABHQEKEKRRGNRAAKINPNTNR-----V-----RASSPPSPQEEAVE	:	312
A. pisum	:	EKSQTQINK-----GSEDLPIBYLTSSLAQQNIQANRKTDEELREBEELQALALSQSEABQKQKIPFMNSTSIPATRL-----YS-----SPPVNEKKIIVEAED	:	308
B. mori	:	DKYSRPPST-----AKLEITDTSNDYGPIT-----QPQK-RPPGGKTAELQEEELQALALSQSEABHKEKERSRPHIAPDPTPHRP-----NIST-----TPSSVSASPEHSTQA	:	313
D. melanogaster	:	AALQRFPSGGGAKSGPRPADSELPABYLSNLT-AQQQ-QTPARKTQELREBEELQALALSQSEABQKQKIPFMNSTSIPATRL-----YS-----SPPVNEKKIIVEAED	:	320
D. plexippus	:	DKYSRPPST-----AKLEIVDTSNDYGPA-----QPQK-RP-GKSABELQEEELQALALSQSEABHKEKERSRPHIAPDPTPHRP-----NIST-----TPSSVSASPEHST-A	:	309
P. corporis	:	EKYSRPPST-----VYKLENEPFDSPQNSSALKTQ-PSKPKTDEELREBEELQALALSQSEABAKEKEREKKAAMITNEIFNNTTSKKSPT-----ITFALIKFKEEED	:	307
S. frugiperda	:	DKYSRPPST-----TKLEIVDTSNDYGPS-----VQTK-KRTGGKTAELQEEELQALALSQSEABHKEKERSRPHIAPDPTPHRP-----NIST-----TPSSVSASPEHSTQA	:	312
T. castaneum	:	DLATKSSGK-----ADKQESLEPPBYNSL-AQQS-QTPPKSDEELREBEELQALALSQSEABAKEKEREKFMWNTY-----KAP-----V-----RS-----PSPQ-----PEQA	:	304
S. cerevisiae	:	EDYDLKRHDDSKS-KKRRHKKKRDY-----STPEDELELRKALSLRERNSA-----SPEIPVVSVEKNEVKKQIEEIEE	:	302

H. sapiens	:	DPDLARVLRNRYEQRKQEARSPVAPVLTPEAAQGEHGAAPTNNVENLPELTDSPQIPPSGPPFSEPFQH-NGESESHEQLKALQNAVITFVVRMKSNSRGRSISND	:	436
A. gambiae	:	DPDLARVLRNRYEQRQVMESP-----ASPSAPS-----PMPSP-----PSLQP-SLLMTK-SAPEDAEDDFNSMNMKTQVEIFVVRMKSNSRGRSISND	:	408
A. mellifera	:	DPDLARVLRNRYEQRQVMESP-----ASPSAPS-----PMPSP-----SPMPQKVIITKQQ-NGEVDNQEEFVNALRSQVEIFVVRMKSNSRGRSISND	:	402
A. pisum	:	DPDLARVLRNRYEQRQVMESP-----ASPSAPS-----PMPSP-----T-----NVNTIESPNEISPAMNNE-QSDDSEELFITSSVKSQVEIFVVRMKSNSRGRSISND	:	398
B. mori	:	NADLSVLRNRYEQRQVMESP-----ASPSAPS-----PMPSP-----ASNTAEDFTKSTAKAQD-DAEDKEDDFDITLKSQVEIFVVRMKSNSRGRSISND	:	405
D. melanogaster	:	NADLSVLRNRYEQRQVMESP-----ASPSAPS-----PMPSP-----TP-----QPQQ-IMPLQV-KSADEVQIDFPAANMKTQVEIFVVRMKSNSRGRSISND	:	406
D. plexippus	:	NADLSVLRNRYEQRQVMESP-----ASPSAPS-----PMPSP-----TNETPDQDFTKSTKQGE-DEADKEDDFVLESKSQVEIFVVRMKSNSRGRSISND	:	398
P. corporis	:	DPDLARVLRNRYEQRQVMESP-----ASPSAPS-----PMPSP-----SAP-----TTPHQLQEN-GEIIESELDDFVSYLKSQVEIFVVRMKSNSRGRSISND	:	398
S. frugiperda	:	NADLSVLRNRYEQRQVMESP-----ASPSAPS-----PMPSP-----A-SDTTEFPKPTTKAQD-EDAEDKEDDFVLESKSQVEIFVVRMKSNSRGRSISND	:	402
T. castaneum	:	DPDLARVLRNRYEQRQVMESP-----ASPSAPS-----PMPSP-----TAPATEITKPKHKE-NGVVDNDEEFTSTLKSQVEIFVVRMKSNSRGRSISND	:	393
S. cerevisiae	:	DPDLARVLRNRYEQRQVMESP-----ASPSAPS-----PMPSP-----SPQPPHSHVLSLDEEKDSELYMFA-----SLVFKMKSRLP-NELEDE	:	379

H. sapiens	:	SAVLSLQSTNGHPQLLELNLLEFRRLYEGLQDKLQTRDARGALSALRETRERLRAAABAERQRQLQAKLEI-MRKKKQYLYQYGR-----LAIQLRQEQER	:	541
A. gambiae	:	SAVQTLFMMNLTTHSRLLRTRQADDKRYVLESQDKLQTRDARGALSALRETRERLRAAABAERQRQLQAKLEI-MRKKKQYLYQYGR-----VALQRIQEQER	:	513
A. mellifera	:	SAVQTLFMMNLTTHSRLLRTRQADDKRYVLESQDKLQTRDARGALSALRETRERLRAAABAERQRQLQAKLEI-MRKKKQYLYQYGR-----LAIQLRQEQER	:	507
A. pisum	:	GSVDLFRSKLTPMHSRLRTRQADDKRYVLESQDKLQTRDARGALSALRETRERLRAAABAERQRQLQAKLEI-MRKKKQYLYQYGR-----LAIQLRQEQER	:	503
B. mori	:	SAVQTLFMMNLTTHSRLLRTRQADDKRYVLESQDKLQTRDARGALSALRETRERLRAAABAERQRQLQAKLEI-MRKKKQYLYQYGR-----LAIQLRQEQER	:	510
D. melanogaster	:	SAVQTLFMMNLTTHSRLLRTRQADDKRYVLESQDKLQTRDARGALSALRETRERLRAAABAERQRQLQAKLEI-MRKKKQYLYQYGR-----LAIQLRQEQER	:	511
D. plexippus	:	TSVQTLFMMNLTTHSRLLRTRQADDKRYVLESQDKLQTRDARGALSALRETRERLRAAABAERQRQLQAKLEI-MRKKKQYLYQYGR-----LAIQLRQEQER	:	503
P. corporis	:	SAVQTLFMMNLTTHSRLLRTRQADDKRYVLESQDKLQTRDARGALSALRETRERLRAAABAERQRQLQAKLEI-MRKKKQYLYQYGR-----LAIQLRQEQER	:	503
S. frugiperda	:	SAVQTLFMMNLTTHSRLLRTRQADDKRYVLESQDKLQTRDARGALSALRETRERLRAAABAERQRQLQAKLEI-MRKKKQYLYQYGR-----LAIQLRQEQER	:	507
T. castaneum	:	TSVQTLFMMNLTTHSRLLRTRQADDKRYVLESQDKLQTRDARGALSALRETRERLRAAABAERQRQLQAKLEI-MRKKKQYLYQYGR-----LAIQLRQEQER	:	498
S. cerevisiae	:	SKLNLAAQRFASKARLYNALN-----LKAQKNTLTEMNGKSEIMNLYRLLEQLQSLN-----LSQYTLPCQPSDPYNTLNTENPNPAESYQTPPLQQLSSHY	:	478

Extended Figure S4

Figure S4. Yeast-two hybrid analysis of the interaction between Vps4 or Vta1 of *S. frugiperda* and BV-envelope proteins of AcMNPV. A 10-fold dilution of yeast cells were plated. DDO, SD/-Leu/-Trp; QDO, SD/-Ade/-His/-Leu/-Trp. The ESCRT-III component Ist1 of *S. frugiperda* and Lef3 of AcMNPV were used as the positive and negative control, respectively.

Extended Figure S5

Figure S5. Western blot analysis of the expression of Nm- and Cm-fused Vps4 and Vta1 of *S. frugiperda*, and BV envelope proteins of AcMNPV. Sf9 cells in 12-well plates (2×10^5 cells/well) were transfected with the transient expression plasmid encoding the fused protein ($2 \mu\text{g}/\text{well}$ for each plasmid) using a standard CaPO_4 precipitation method. At 36 h p.t., the cells were lysed with RIPA buffer containing

the complete protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche Diagnostics GmbH) and the proteins were separated on 12% or 15% SDS-PAGE gels. Then, the proteins were transferred to PVDF membrane (0.45 μ m, GVS) and detected using the mAb anti-HA 12CA5 (Bioss) (for the Nm-fused protein, which contains the HA epitope tag) or anti-Myc 2G8D5 (Genscript) (for the Cm-fused protein, which contains the c-Myc epitope tag), the alkaline phosphatase-conjugated goat anti-mouse IgG (H+L) secondary antibody (Promega) and the BCIP/NBT color development kit (Coolaber). Nm and Cm represent the N- and C-terminal domain of mCherry, respectively.

Extended Figure S6

Figure S6. One-step growth curves of wild-type (wt) AcMNPV and Ac93-HA-Cm-repaired ac93-knockout virus. Sf9 cells were infected with each of the virus (MOI=5) and the virus titers were measured by a 50% tissue culture infection dose (TCID₅₀) assay at indicated time points. Error bars represent SD from the mean of three replicates.